

Lattice strain induced structural phase evolution in BNT-BNZ solid solution

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Abstract

The polycrystalline lead free (1-x) Bi_{0.5}Na_{0.5}TiO₃-(x)Bi_{0.5}Na_{0.5}ZrO₃ [BNT-BZT] with x= 0.10-0.50 based solid solutions have been prepared by the high temperature solid state ceramic method. X-ray diffraction analysis confirms the formation of single phase stable perovskite compound. Structural phase transition from rhombohedral (*R3c*) to orthorhombic (*Pnma*) crystal symmetry with the increase of mole fraction of Zr⁴⁺ in BNT has been observed from the Rietveld refinement of XRD patterns. The structural evolution between *R3c* and *Pnma* crystal symmetries in the present solid solutions can be well explained by assuming the lattice strain in the crystal structure. It is basically due to the mismatch of ionic radii between titanium (Ti⁴⁺~0.60pm) and zirconium (Zr⁴⁺~0.72pm). Also, variation of the crystal symmetries of the solid solutions has been correlated with Goldschmidt tolerance factor (t). The microstructure of the solid solutions is analyzed by the field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM), which confirmed the formation of dense ceramic with non-uniform grain size. Room temperature Raman spectra of all the solid solutions have been investigated to confirm the structural phase transition by observing the variation in different mode of phonon vibrations. The room temperature dielectric permittivity of the solid solutions has been measured in the frequency range from 100 Hz to 1MHz. It is observed that the composition with x =0.35 exhibits maximum dielectric constant, which is identified as morphotropic phase boundary composition.

Keywords: Dielectric, Rietveld, XRD, Crystal structure, Lattice strain